

Perceptions of Sportswomen Participation in Sports at the University Level: A Case Study of Shaheed Benazir Bhutto Women University Peshawar

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: January 28, 2023</p> <p>Accepted: April 30, 2023</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Sportswomen, Sports Activities, Participation, Physical and Mental Health, Challenges, Women University.</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10015851</p>	<p><i>Sport is ideal for both physical and mental health. It supports individuals in improving their lifestyle. Individuals doing physical and sports activities since from their childhood may improve several aspects of their personality. Sport works upon developing individuals leadership skills and qualities and enhance their strength of decision making. However in a country like Pakistan women participation in sports is not encouraged. The current study explores the perception of sportswomen about their participation in sports at university level. The sample of this qualitative research comprises fourteen sports women each as a case study from Shaheed Benazir Bhutto Women University Peshawar. An in-depth semi-structured interview schedule was used to get the relevant information from the sampled sportswomen at university level. Thematic approach was used for the analysis of data. Interviews with the sportswomen revealed that all sportswomen respondents who were interviewed belonged to lower middle class where they already were facing challenges. From the very beginning they faced problems in convincing their parents who were reluctant about their doing sports. Besides that, sportswomen feel uncomfortable for receiving negative comments from community both inside university and outside university from friends, teachers, other students at university and overall people of the community. Furthermore, they face economic challenges due to which they were unable to participate in international tournament, like transport expenses, proper healthy diet and obtaining sports provisions (like specific shoes and other specific sports equipment's). For acknowledging and supporting sportswomen, both government and university administration should work upon facilitating students through grants and scholarships for their contribution and in representation of their institutions at city, district, provincial, national, and international level.</i></p>

Introduction

Sports in schools, colleges and universities develop several skills in individuals. If all students are given equal opportunities in physical and sports activities, it will help in shaping up their future personalities. However, in countries like Pakistan women are not enjoying sports opportunities as compared to men. It means women are still not allowed like men to enjoy and participate in physical and sports activities in Pakistan and especially in provinces like Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (Khan et al., 2012).

Fazal et al., (2019) argued that the role of sports and physical activities in developing the personality of individuals has been reported by many studies (Laar et al., 2019a, Laar et al., 2019b). Besides that, women's equivalence is a concept according to which women ought to be given chance of choosing things in their everyday life, like men it provides a solid basis for the rights of women and the same was endorsed by Hargreaves (1994). Equal opportunity for women creates an environment within which women can make careful decisions and conscious life judgments in specific situations.

Klasen, (2006) stated that of the total world population women shape almost 1/2 of it, and women's enablement is therefore taken into consideration as a critical element in attaining the maximum level of desired development (Upadhyay et al., 2014).

Bradshaw, (2002) stated that the idea of empowering women through sports activities and bodily interest has grown to be a device for uniting women in their struggle against masculine customs regarding women's choices regarding their lives and bodies.

Peters et al., (2008) argued that women's deliverance via physical activity is a critical detail for a wholesome lifestyle, in each advanced and growing countries (Cronin et al., 2019). Women through healthy physical activities may shape up their future life. The everyday belief of bodily interest directed the

improvement of worldwide and community guidelines for women's involvement in sports activities and bodily pastimes.

Women in Pakistan legally enjoy equal rights concerning their name, voting, education, social and political contribution, and participation in physical activities. In Pakistan as stated by National Institute of Population Studies (2019) sports activities and bodily sports are even so much ignored from the debates surrounding women's equality or liberation in Pakistan. Quran the Holy Book of the religion of Islam and the conventions of the Prophet Muhammad (Hadiths) support physical activity as an important part of the development of human health. Islam says about fitness and good health are explained as a solid blessing (Khan et al., 2012).

Bakhtiar et al., (2007) illustrated that regardless of gender differences, Islam focuses on the growth and safeguard of bodily and spiritual powers. Muslims are clearly encouraged by Islam to guide their children to analyse various bodily sports that will transform them into a vigorous and energetic individual.

Muslim et al., (2007) and Khan et al., (2012) highlighted that the Prophet Muhammad (PBUH) stated that Muslims must educate their children in acquiring knowledge of the civilizations of swimming, horse riding, and throwing arrows. Although physical activity is encouraged for all Muslims, including women.

Laar et al., (2019a) elaborated that however in some of the non-secular states where the cultural rules are dominated women are not allowed to participate in physical activities or sports activities, and in such kind of situations they don't even are given a space to keep some good hobbies as a leisure time activities.

Edim and Saba, (2014) informed that just like in other Muslim nationals where women are facing problems in physical and sports activities about wearing modest dress, women too in Pakistan are facing such kind of wearing modest dress issues which are not harmonious with religion of Islam. Further they stated that besides that the women too are facing the lack of sports activities., cultural issues, social issues, economic issues, lack of family support, lack of public interest, and lack of grants and funds etc., due to which women sports is badly affected.

Laar et al., (2019a) reported about the same social, cultural, economic, lack of interest of government, lack of family support etc., all are considered primary elements due to which are badly affecting women's sports.

Hargreaves, (2002) stated that people are in clash with the belief that Islam is not allowing women for sports activities, and if they are doing such kind of physical or sports activities than this is totally against Islam, which is not true and which is totally wrong perception which people have adopted themselves and they are interpreting the aspect of Islam about sports in a totally absurd way. He further clarified that Islam is not against the participation of women's' in physical and sports activities.

Dagkas et al., (2011) endorsed the same opinion that by no means there is any condition in the Quran that stops women from contributing and joining in sports activities, this is the wrong interpretation of phrases of modesty that women are unable to satisfy the necessities required for doing sports from Islamic point of view. so long as girls satisfy the requirements in phrases of modesty.

Bennal et. al. (2010) the same matter by emphasizing that the provision of equal chances to women in sports needs to be matched with the Islamic framework in terms of wearing modest costumes. Another cultural norm that indicates is the fear of de-feminization due to participation in sports activities. Women are strongly influenced by the practices of cultural protection through socialization, and therefore, women avoid being involved in sports and physical activities. Like other disciplines, the sport needs a co-curriculum schedule due in the current situation, most of our people are to understand the advantage of sports science in different aspects. It gives both males and females an overall advantage in human beings that is mental and physical development. Sports are organized activities played individually or in teams. Men and women can play most sports. Many people participate in sports as professionals for personal enjoyment, the love of competition, or as a healthful form of exercise. Sport presents enjoyment for human beings at some point of the world.

The study helps in gathering information about the general features of sports and the need for spreading sport knowledge about participation of sportswomen at university level in sports activities or physical activities Furthermore, this study explores about the challenges faced in adopting sports activities at university level. In the same way it provides suggestions in improving women's participation in sports at higher level.

Objectives of the Study

- i. To discover the sports background of sportswomen at the university level.
- ii. To investigate the sportswomen's interest in study and sports at the university level.
- iii. To explore the challenges they face as sportswomen at the university level.

Research Questions

The research study was guided by the following questions:

- i. What are the perceptions of sportswomen about their participation in sports at university level?
- ii. What are the background and interests of sportswomen in sports and studies at the university level?
- iii. What sort of challenges students face as sportswomen at the university level?

Methodology

This study was designed to explore the perceptions of sportswomen at the university level about their participation in sports available at the women university (SBBWUP). The study was designed as a qualitative exploratory research design and a case study of single women university in Peshawar from the province of Khyber-Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan.

Population

The population of this research study included all the sportswomen of Shaheed Benazir Bhutto Women University Peshawar.

Sample Size and Its Distribution

Fourteen sportswomen were selected from the Health and Physical Education Department at Shaheed Benazir Bhutto Women University Peshawar. A non-probability sampling method with both snowball and convenience-purposive sampling techniques were used. A sample of fourteen sportswomen were selected completely on voluntary basis.

Data Collection Instrument

Semi-structured in-depth interview schedule was adopted for collecting relevant data. Sportswomen were interviewed about their perception on participation in sports activities, their sports background, interests in sports and studies and challenges faced by them as a sportswoman at university level.

Results and Discussion

The results are stated to elucidate that how sportswomen at university level perceptions were about their participation in sports activities, their sports background, their interests in sports and studies and challenges faced by them as sportswomen in community around them. In this context the following research questions are mentioned with result and discussion.

Background and Interests of some of the Respondent Sportswomen in Sports and Studies

Respondent 1

Iqra Ishaq is a sports woman. She is currently studying at Shaheed Benazir Bhutto Women's University Peshawar in the 5th semester of Health and Physical Education (H&PE). She is always receiving first position in her class from the day of her admission in this university. She is a passionate sportswoman who participates in multiple types of sports activities available in the university. She is a National Badminton Player. She is 22 years old and lives in Peshawar (urban). She has five sisters and one brother. Her father did matriculation and is a tailor master. Her mother is illiterate and working as an assistant job with a children's specialist. She is the first generation of her family studying at university. Currently along with her studies she is participating in different tournaments at district and national level.

Respondent 2

Sana Younas is a sportswoman. She is 23 years old, and she belongs to Bannu (rural) but currently, they live in Peshawar (city) due to her father's job and her education. She recently completed her BS (Hons) at H&PE department at Shaheed Benazir Bhutto Women's University. She is an all-rounder cricket player. She is the first generation of her family studying at university. Her father is a government employee, and his education is B.Com. And her mother is a housewife and illiterate. In siblings she has 3 sisters and 3 brothers. She is passionate about continuing her study and hopes to do MS in Health & Physical Education from abroad.

Respondent 3

Amna is a sportswoman. She is 19 years old. She is currently studying at Shaheed Benazir Bhutto Women University Peshawar in the 1st semester of Health and Physical Education (HPE). Her father is a police inspector, and her mother is a housewife. She has 5 brothers and one sister. She orders third among her siblings. She is all-rounder cricket player at university level. Besides cricket she is an all-rounder sports player. She is very passionate about playing hockey. In future she wants to become a robust sports candidate and play internationally and represent Pakistan. She wants to become an international player both in hockey and cricket. Her future goal is to become a sports instructor and practice with students to motivate them for joining all kinds of physical and sports activities.

Theme 1: Sportswomen Interest in Studies and Sports

While inquired about their Interest and Studies in Sports some of them responded in following words:

"I can easily manage my time for sports and studies. I always stand 1st in all my semesters.

"I can easily manage my study time and my sports time. My sports activities are not affecting my studies. I always had first position in my class and I don't understand that why people think that while doing sports people fail to focus on their studies".

"I am an average student sometimes I get good grades in my class and sometimes I don't get good grades in the class".

Theme 2: Sports Activities in the University

“Yes, they should update the things but, in our university, almost every kind of sports is available like Table Tennis, Squash, Badminton, Volleyballs, Cricket, Taekwondo, fencing, Net Ball etc”

“In our university, every sport is available like Table tennis, Squash, Badminton, Volleyballs, Cricket, Net Ball, taekwondo, fencing etc. I suggest providing equal opportunities to all the sports girls will be good instead of going for any kind of favouritism.”

“There is a fencing game newly introduced by our sports instructor in our university, we are practicing this game in Shaheen Shah Gym. It was entirely new kind of experience for me. My experience was really good this was the easiest game and it do not require too much stamina; one would play it just for 30 minutes”

“As a sportswoman I would suggest my university that they should focus on polishing all the female students (from all departments) and give them confidence to participate in all different kinds of sports activities already available at the university.”

Theme 3: Challenges Faced as Sportswomen at the University Level

The following challenges were highlighted by the respondents:

“Sometimes I do face problems, but my teachers are cooperative and here in university they help us and support us in any kind of difficult situations”.

Teachers play a great role in the life of a student. As a university student and as a sports woman they get support and good response from their teachers. Which serves a lot for them and now they can do sports along with their academics.

“People give negative comments about us, but I don’t know maybe I have good mind and character whatever they say does not bother me. However, here in this university, I’m not facing any kind of issues as being a sportswoman, as initially I wanted to do MBBS but due to some financial issues, I wasn’t able to pursue it. Now I want to do MS in Health and Physical Education at this university but here I can’t see the opportunity of MS in HPE department. I love this university this is a very comfortable zone for me., it offered me lots of sports opportunities and I’m comfortable here when I’m in my kit.”

Respondent said that people in society give negative comments about us, but as she has got a strong personality, so she doesn’t care so much about such kind of things. She wanted to become a doctor but due financial issues she was unable to fulfil her dream. She joined this university and took admission in the department of Health and Physical Education. She feels herself quite happy and protected in this university but as the department is not offering any further higher education like MS and PhD in H&PE, so she is deciding to do MS from abroad for making it as her career in future.

“When I was in college, I was playing volleyball, but I did not get any scholarship from this college, so I stopped playing this game the college was in district Charsadda and at that time I lived in Peshawar so may be that was the reason they were not giving me any scholarship. Being a sportswoman, I can face the problem when I come late at home due to these sports activities my family says than where you were, or if you have guests or relatives at home than they look at you with inquiring gestures.”

One another respondent mentioned that she played volleyball during her college life, but she didn’t get any scholarship for this sport, so she stopped playing it as she was demotivated. As she was from Peshawar and she was living in Charsadda district at that time due to her father job, so may be due to this reason she was deprived from scholarship at this college. As a sportswoman she also faces problem due to her late coming at home due to practice session for tournaments etc.

Hallmann, Wicker, Breuer, & Schönherr, (2012) stated that the sports field is influenced in different countries due to inexperience staff, inappropriate fields or grounds, maladministration, deficiency of trained instructors and inappropriate economic conditions. All these adverse conditions have worsened the sports programs in general. Due to adverse economic conditions as stated previously many of sports players are not facilitated with sports gears. As doing sports is a good thing. But what if on one hand it is expensive and, on the hand, someone is passionate of doing it. The same feeling is expressed by one of respondent as below.

“Yes, I do face some financial problems, while as a badminton player I buy for myself a shuttle box which is expensive, and one shuttle price is (3500/-). So, when all my shuttles get damaged it is too expensive for me to purchase a new box. My track shoes, sports suits or dresses, and transport fair all this is very expensive for me”

Respondent stated about facing some of the financial problems. As a badminton player she faces problem in arranging a new shuttle box for herself, this is because she belongs to a lower middle class. Besides that, she shared about facing financial problems in arranging sports shoes, sports suits, and transport expenses.

“From the very start when I was in my college and doing sports, I was facing financial problems. During first year of my college, I played only cricket. And then in 2nd year, I started playing cricket, netball, handball, and baseball. Whenever any tournament used to be nearer and for such kind of matches or games players were to be arranged in almost all the

groups because there are not a lot of players (or girls playing sports) both in college and university so they can't make separate teams. In our university as there are not a lot of players, so we participate almost in all games for representing our university (in all sports matches here at the same time). About financial problems I would say yes, I really feel difficulty in purchasing track shoes, and sports dress. And the transport is also very expensive for me. Here I want to share that last year there was a baseball international tournament in Thailand I was selected for it but when I was told to arrange ticket for myself which was not that much easy for me, so then I decided not to go. I think government is responsible for arranging and facilitating sports women from poor background. Although for any national tournament government provide to the sportswomen a sports kit, lunch and shoes or give us (600Rs), which I think is not enough for a player."

Respondent shared that when it comes for sports, I would say yes, I do face financial problems in this regard. If you belong to a lower middle class or poor family and you are a sports lover than I can't place all my necessities burden on my family, so I used to manage all this from my pocket money. As they are playing at the same time several games, which requires a specific sports kit etc. Besides that, her track shoes, sportswear, and transport fair all are expensive for her. Not only that due to her financial problems she quit from international tournament in Thailand as she was unable to manage or bear the ticket expenses. Government should work on facilitating more sportswomen from lower middle class or poor families.

"Yes, I face financial problems in hockey I buy gripper shoes which cost me rupees 4000 Rs, and it is too much expensive for me to buy it. Besides that, as a sports person you need healthy diet and extra diet for making your muscles strong. So due to financial issues I try myself to not put my parents in trouble and I rely on any kind of food available at home. I realize about all those things that, and I don't want to keep burden on my parent that I want this thing for my fitness. I think if we are internally strong then we are externally healthy. University do not give us any kind money for our sports but when we won a tournament the cash price of 50,000 as a winner we receive was for the whole team, and it was distributed among all the players, and I received 4,000 maximums. If our university or government arrange some scholarships for the sportswomen, then we can easily manage all the sports equipment easily, like shoes, sports suit, sports kit etc.....Well, we are hoping for some good things as Khyber Pakhtunkhwa director at sports complex have mention that they will start scholarship for sportswomen." (Amna, HP&E Department 1st Semester)

One of respondent voiced that she is facing financial problems as she is playing hockey for which she needs wear gripper shoes which are expensive for her and it costs her nearly about 4000 Rs, which according to her is too much expensive to buy. Besides that, as for such kind of muscular activities they need to take care of their physical health and make their muscles, and which is not possible without good food. Amna claims that all these things are very expensive, so besides putting her family in trouble she can eat anything available for eating at home. She thought that if you are strong from inside than everything goes well, and this is her belief of being successful as a sportswoman. She further stated that there should be some aid for sportswomen from university or government so that they can easily manage all their basic needs of sports. Right now, what they are having from their own pocket money and little bit cash they get as a winner team in any tournament as the cash amount they get is distributed among all the players. So, there is need of understanding such kinds of problems of all sportswomen and they should be given proper scholarships. Johnson et al. (2001) stated that the lack of female participation in sports is due to economic pressure, and the same is endorsed by Shores et al., (2007) and Walseth and Strandbu, (2014).

Discussion

The findings of the study showed that all the interviewee (sportswomen) who were interviewed belonged to lower middle class where they were already facing so many challenges. From the very beginning they faced problems in convincing their parents who were reluctant about their doing sports. The respondents (sportswomen) shared that they cannot afford good quality or healthy kind of food and they rely on eating anything available to them whether it comes under quality or not. However, still they play with the belief that when they have inner strength then they are strong enough to play every kind of sports. The participants said that the culture of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa and especially of Peshawar is not very much typical now parents are supporting and taking interest in sports and allowing their girls to participate in physical and sports activities, however relatives and from community do create some problems. Sportswomen shared about their feelings that they feel so proud whenever they play these games. They can easily manage their time for sports and studies. They further stated that our university already offers several different kinds of games and sports like; table tennis, squash, badminton, volleyball, cricket, netball, handball, hockey, baseball, kabaddi, dancing, taekwondo, rugby, fencing game etc. As according to one of the respondent (sportswoman) who stated that I'm quite sure that most of the women of this university are not aware of all these different kinds of sports available at our

university. There is need of disseminating information and awareness about all kinds of sports available at university. To add further it is a matter of grave concern that majority of the sportswomen who were most of the time busy in doing different kinds of sports belonged to the only H&PE department. It is suggested that women from other departments must participate as well in all the sports activities available at the university. Along with that society should realize its role and give importance to the women sports and equal rights should be given to everyone at the higher institutional level of education. To add, several studies reported that women from Muslim countries shows less participation in sports activities as compared to other countries of the world (Di-Capua, 2005; Klein, 2007 & Mirsafian et al. 2014). Even though in some urban regions of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa the people are now showing some flexibility about the women participation in sports.

Implications

- i. The results of the study may help in exploring the gaps that need to be worked on and will enlighten all the stake holders with a new perception about sportswomen.
- ii. The findings of the study will serve as a road map for the stakeholders while designing strategies in the curriculum for women sports programs at higher level.

Recommendations

There is need of working on following notions, that may be used comprehensively by the government, women university administrators, policy makers, university faculty, community, parents, and students themselves to work together for developing healthy practices about sports activities at university.

- i) All the concerned authorities along with the faculty of the university need to work together for sports activities and develop among students their self-confidence to eagerly participate in all kinds of sports activities available at university.
- ii) Students from all departments may participate in different physical and sports activities available at university.
- iii) For acknowledging and supporting sportswomen, both government and university administration should work upon facilitating them through grants and scholarships for their contribution and in representation of their institutions at city, district, provincial, national, and international level.
- iv) All women universities may put themselves in struggle to learn more about the importance of sports activities for promoting healthy learning environment among university women.

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